

PREVIEW

PREreview Champions' Handbook 2026

Contents

Contents	2
Welcome	3
The PREreview Champions Program	4
Expectations of PREreview Champions	6
What Champions can expect from PREreview	9
The PREreview Champions Mentor Program	9
Resources	10
Branding	10
PREreview Champions Program Badge	10
Workshops & Events	10
2-hour workshop	11
Multi-session workshops	11
The Open Reviewers Toolkit	11
Templates	12
Event Planning Checklist	12
Live Reviews	15
Who participates?	15
What are the event outputs?	15
Resources for running a collaborative Live Review	15
PREreview Clubs	16
Using the PREreview.org website	16
Finding a preprint to review	17
Getting started reviewing	18
Using Zoom (or other video conferencing software)	19
Using Slack	21
About PREreview	23
Our Mission	23
Our Values	23
Our Team	24
How we are supported	25
Funders and sponsors	25
Other Useful Links	25
Other Resources	26

Welcome

Thank you for volunteering to be a PREreview Champion! We are thrilled to be working with you and hope that you also gain as much from being a member of our 2026 Champions Program cohort as we do from your help in engaging the scholarly research community in open, preprint peer review!

The Champions Handbook is designed to be a helpful guide to ensure that you have what you need to succeed in your role as a PREreview Champion. It includes information about the mission and work of PREreview, the Champions' Program, the training workshops, templates, and helpful links to find all the information you might need.

We will keep this handbook updated, and we are open to any suggestions for extra things to include. So if you have any suggestions for improvements, please email them to the PREreview team at champions@prereview.org.

The PREreview Champions Program

Three early-career, female scientists—Daniela Saderi, Monica Granados, and Samantha Hindle—co-founded PREreview to address the lack of diversity and transparency within scholarly peer review and to empower marginalized researchers to engage in the open review of preprints. The PREreview Champions Program, launched in 2024, aims to empower individuals who share this mission with the knowledge, skills, and resources to train and engage others to participate in the open peer review of preprints.

The program spans 12 months and includes selection, onboarding, training, engagement activities, and final reporting. Champions receive the PREreview Open Reviewers Workshop with a focus on how to adapt the materials to their own contexts and train others within their local communities. The workshop series provides practical guidance on writing reviews alongside how to address issues of bias and systemic oppression within peer review, and general facilitation and event organization guidance. In the six months following the training, Champions complete at least one engagement activity, such as leading workshops, delivering talks, organizing collaborative Live Reviews, or mentoring peers.

Alongside this handbook with guidelines, templates, and resources, you also have access to a [shared drive for collaboration](#), as well as a dedicated [Slack channel](#), and we will hold regular cohort catch-up calls so that you have the opportunity to get to know your fellow Champions, ask questions, collaborate, solve challenges, and celebrate successes.

Participation Guidelines & Code of Conduct

In the interest of fostering an open and brave environment we, as leadership, contributors, and maintainers, pledge to make participation in our project and our community a harassment-free experience for everyone, regardless of background, family status, gender, gender identity, or expression, marital status, sex, sexual orientation, native language, age, ability, race and/or ethnicity, caste, national origin, socioeconomic status, religion, geographic location, and any other dimension of diversity.

Expected behaviors

Example behaviors of PREreview Champions and all PREreview community members include:

- Being respectful of differing viewpoints and experiences
- Being open to different possibilities and being wrong

- Using welcoming and inclusive language. Encourage all voices. Help new perspectives to be heard, and listen actively
- Providing feedback that is constructive
- Gracefully accepting constructive criticism
- Focusing on what is best for the community
- Showing empathy towards other community members
- Respecting the privacy and confidentiality of everyone in the community
- Maintaining kindness, professionalism, and integrity in all of your interactions

Particularly in the role of PREreview Champion, you act as a representative of PREreview, and your actions influence others to behave and respond in ways that are valuable and appropriate for our shared outcomes. Hold yourself and others accountable for inclusive behaviors. These behaviors are expected regardless of whether the interaction occurs within our Slack Community, training workshops, via email, or any other online or in-person interaction as part of the PREreview community.

Prohibited behaviors

Examples of unacceptable behaviors by participants include, but are not limited to:

- Violence and threats of violence
- Trolling, insulting/derogatory comments, and personal or political attacks
- The use of sexualized language or imagery and unwelcome sexual attention or advances;
- Public or private harassment
- Publishing others' private information, such as a physical or electronic address, without explicit permission
- Providing unconstructive or disruptive feedback on PREreview
- Posting spam or irrelevant material
- Influencing unacceptable behavior
- Reviewing your own preprint
- Recording and/or sharing content from PREreview training sessions and events without permission
- Other conduct that could reasonably be considered inappropriate in a professional setting

Instances of abusive, harassing, or otherwise unacceptable behavior should be reported by filling out our [report form](#) with the option to be anonymous, emailing report@prereview.org, or

by messaging [@safety](#) on the PREreview Community Slack. In the report, please describe the violation of this Code of Conduct and the context in which it occurred. The more detail you provide, the easier it will be for us to act on the reported misconduct.

If you email us, please use “**Code of Conduct Violation Report**” as your subject line. If you decide to report the violation via the form and you wish us to follow up with you, please be sure to include your email address at the end of the form.

All complaints will be reviewed and investigated, and will result in a response determined by the **PREreview Safety Team**. The PREreview Safety Team consists of PREreview’s Executive Director, Head of Community, Head of Product, and Head of Technology. To view the complete response protocol, please refer to our [Code of Conduct](#) page on the PREreview website. Please note that Code of Conduct violations may result in you no longer being allowed to participate in the PREreview Champions Program.

Expectations of PREreview Champions

PREreview Champions are provided with the PREreview Open Reviewers Workshop training and are expected to attend all of the virtual training sessions (with reasonable accommodations to be made where needed). The Champions’ Program Workshop differs from the standard Open Reviewers Workshop in that it focuses on providing Champions with the skills and knowledge to train others in the content. Module I sets the scene with a focus on the impact of personal and structural bias in peer review. Module II provides more practical guidance on how to train others in providing constructive, clear, and actionable feedback to a research manuscript, and Module III focuses on event logistics and human-centered facilitation tips.

After the training concludes, we run a number of [Live Review](#) sessions to put the knowledge gained into practice by reviewing a preprint collaboratively as a group. These sessions also include learning how to lead a collaborative review session and an opportunity to provide feedback and suggestions for improvements to the process. The collaborative review generated from the session will have a DOI, and review authors will have the option to be named and recognized in the scholarly record.

You can find the workshop slides, collaborative notes documents, recordings, and transcripts from the training sessions in the [PREreview Champions 2026 Shared Google Drive](#). Please

contact champions@prereview.org if you have any issues accessing the shared drive or any of the materials.

After the training concludes, PREreview Champions are expected to complete at least one follow-on engagement activity **by the end of September 2026**. It is important to us that our Champions contribute in ways that they feel comfortable, according to their interests, skills, and the time they feel they can contribute. For this reason, the role comes with a high degree of flexibility. Follow-on activities Champions may undertake include, but are not limited to:

- Translating PREreview materials and resources into other languages
- Running an Open Reviewers training either online or in-person
- Mentoring three or more fellow researchers on how to review a preprint, with the reviews published on PREreview.org
- Organizing and facilitating one or more Live Reviews
- Creating and leading a new PREreview Club
- Organizing and/or speaking about PREreview at an in-person or virtual event
- Organizing a panel discussion about open preprint review
- Facilitating a collaboration between PREreview with another like-minded program or organization
- Helping us to run a global PREreview day where reviewers around the world get together to review preprints

The [CSCCE Community Participation Model \(CPM\)](#) below is a useful tool for thinking about how different members of a community interact and describes four modes of community member participation: Convey/Consume, Contribute, Collaborate, and Co-Create, as well as a fifth “super user” mode, the Champion mode.

Citation: Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2020) The CSCCE Community Participation Model – A framework for member engagement and information flow in STEM communities. Woodley and Pratt doi:10.5281/zenodo.3997802

A community champion may use any of the four core modes described in the CPM in their activities (e.g., CONVEY: they post on social media to spread the word more widely; CONTRIBUTE: they host a local event to bring others together; COLLABORATE: they host a community call; CO-CREATE: they run a workshop training or other activities for others in the community).

If you have any ideas for activities you would like to run, you can always contact us or your fellow Champions via [Slack](#) or email us at community@prereview.org to gather feedback and request any supporting materials.

When you have completed an activity, please log the details in the [activity report form](#).

What Champions can expect from PREreview

We want you as a member of our Champions team to feel comfortable and confident in representing PREreview, be this presenting at a conference, writing a blog article, or providing Open Reviewers training to early-career researchers in your community.

To ensure you feel fully supported and valued in your role, we provide the following:

- \$500 USD honorarium provided upon completion of the training and at least one engagement activity (please note that bank payments may not be possible in some countries; payments may instead be in the form of a gift voucher, please contact us if you have any concerns);
- PREreview Open Reviewers Training, including certification and digital badge of attendance;
- A copy of all workshop materials licensed CC BY 4.0, including workshop information, slides, handouts, and templates;
- Recognition on the PREreview website;
- Help with content for presentations, training, Live Reviews, and written articles;
- Personal PREreview Champion 2026 badge for use on email, website, and profile on the PREreview Slack Community;
- Being included in a supportive community of individuals who share your vision for a more open and equitable scholarly communication landscape.

This list is not exhaustive. If you ever find that you have any questions or require assistance, you can always contact us, and we are happy to provide you with whatever support we can. Below you can also find a list of resources and useful links to help you in your PREreview activities.

The PREreview Champions Mentor Program

Each 2026 PREreview Champion has been matched with a volunteer Mentor –someone who successfully completed this program in the past. Your mentor will help you discover and answer the questions you need to address to imagine, design, build, and facilitate your final activity or project.

You and your Mentor will have an introductory meeting and three check-in meetings about your activity or project once you complete training, as well as a debrief meeting at the end of the program.

You may also use email or Slack (or another preferred method) to communicate asynchronously with your Mentor throughout the program. You will be able to offer feedback via a survey at the end of the program.

If an issue comes up sooner than that, or you need some kind of help, reach out to chad@prereview.org or to report@prereview.org for Code of Conduct issues.

Resources

Below you can find a list of resources to help you in your Champions Program engagement activities. We will keep these updated regularly, so you know that you can trust the information that you share with those in your communities.

Branding

Here you can find the [PREreview Style Guide](#). Please follow these guidelines whenever possible on communications, presentations, publications, and resources.

If you have any questions or need any help styling anything, please contact our Communications and Engagement Officer, Pia Tavella, at pia@prereview.org or post in the [#prereview-champions-2026](#) channel of our Community Slack instance.

PREreview Champions Program Badge

Due to changes in the software we use for issuing badges, this section will be updated with guidance on how to claim your PREreview Champions badge soon.

Workshops & Events

Peer review plays a pivotal role in determining which research projects receive funding, which findings get published, and ultimately, which knowledge is disseminated and utilized by the scientific community and the broader public. Despite its critical importance, reviewers often

undergo minimal training for this crucial task. Furthermore, that training rarely focuses on mitigating the biases that are ingrained in the peer review process. Hence, new generations of reviewers often lack the frameworks to address their biases, leading to a perpetuation of the current inequities in scholarly publishing.

The Open Reviewers Workshop is an interactive and hands-on training program designed for researchers at all career levels who are interested in engaging in ethical and constructive manuscript peer review. With a focus on promoting equity, diversity, and inclusion, the workshop provides participants with the necessary skills and knowledge to conduct constructive peer review with the use of materials from [The Open Reviewers Toolkit](#).

2-hour workshop

This stand-alone introductory workshop focuses on the basics of open, preprint peer review and becoming aware of biases present in the scholarly publication process.

Multi-session workshops

These multi-session trainings run for 4-6 hours and offer greater opportunities for practical review experience following a structured approach to writing a review, keeping issues of bias and systemic oppression front of mind. These workshops culminate in a [Live Review](#) session facilitated by PREreview staff, where participants select and review a preprint together

We hope that after your Champions Program training, you feel adequately equipped to provide Open Reviewers training to others within your community. We list a number of resources below to help you in doing so. Please let us know if you plan on running an Open Reviewers training workshop or another relevant event for your community, and we would be happy to help you with promotion if desired.

The Open Reviewers Toolkit

With a focus on promoting equity, diversity, and inclusion, the [Open Reviewers Workshop](#) is designed for researchers at all career levels who are interested in engaging in ethical and constructive manuscript peer review. The Open Reviewers Toolkit comprises three guides to help with the unbiased composition and assessment of research manuscripts:

- **The Bias Reflection Guide** is a tool to help a reviewer assess their own biases, guiding them through a non-judgmental, self-reflective process. (Available in [English](#) (original), [español](#), and [português brasileiro](#))

- **The Reviewer Guide** is for anyone reviewing a research manuscript. It provides a comprehensive, step-by-step framework for the reviewer to use while they are composing a review. (Available in [English](#) (original) [español](#), and [português brasileiro](#))
- **The Review Assessment Rubric** is for anyone evaluating a research manuscript's review. The rubric comprises 10 statements for which the evaluator is asked to provide a score and a written comment to help improve the review. (Available in [English](#) (original), [español](#) and [português brasileiro](#))

All of our resources are openly available for download on Zenodo under a CC BY 4.0 license.

Templates

Below, you can find the links to templates for the Open Reviewers workshop. These will be updated over time. Whenever using these templates, please **make a copy to work from**, rather than editing the template itself. Feel free to adapt these templates and the content to your audience.

- [About PREreview](#)
- [2-hour Open Reviewers workshop](#)
- [6-hour full Open Reviewers workshop](#)
 - [Module 1 templates](#)
 - [Module 2 templates](#)
 - [Module 3: Live Review templates](#)
- [Survey templates](#) (in Google Forms)
- [Social media promotion template](#) (in Canva)

Event planning checklist

3 months before the event

- Decide location (online or in-person)

- Consider the format ([see some examples](#) here)
- Consider what costs are involved and agree on a budget
- Decide target audience - language, time zone, and level of knowledge
- Decide event dates (check what other activities are planned and any holidays to take into account)
- Decide your content and learning objectives
- Create promotional messaging and imagery
- Confirm trainers and/or speakers (try to involve speakers who bring a diverse range of perspectives)
- Confirm venue (if applicable)
- Set up the event registration page - Gather what you need (e.g. contact details, accessibility requirements, knowledge level, location), but don't ask for additional demographic information that you don't need or make this optional.
- Create a communication plan and template social media posts (translate if required)

1-2 months before the event

- Send out invitation emails
- Promote event
- Finalize the agenda
- Prepare presentation slide decks (translate if required)
- Design materials and activities with the goal of collaboration, participation, and the mutual exchange of opinions and knowledge.
- Prepare follow-up emails and pre and post-workshop surveys (translate if required)
- Send out the pre-workshop survey (if applicable, [template here](#))
- Send out reminder emails to registrants

- For in-person events, prepare any physical materials needed - handouts, name badges, etc.

During the event

- Ensure you have a clear Code of Conduct, ways to report violations, and a follow-up procedure in place (you can find our Code of Conduct at PREreview [here](#))
- Ensure audio and video set-up is working correctly
- If you are recording the event, make sure you have asked attendees' permission to do so.
- Make sure you have a co-facilitator and/or a dedicated person responsible for timekeeping and handling the Q&A/chat
- Structure notes to convey essential information in a written form that others can copy, paste, and translate, and to capture audience input.
- Make a list of links to all the resources mentioned to be shared in the chat (makes it easier to copy and paste during your event)

After the event

- Post-workshop survey to be shared with attendees (if applicable, [template here](#))
- Ensure materials are openly shared, accessible, and reusable (make sure to get the relevant permissions and credit the original creator(s) before sharing)
- Have a call to action and provide clear ways for people to further engage
- Submit your [engagement activity report](#)
- Optionally, write up your event into a blog piece or article.

Please refer to Module III of the PREreview Champions Program for more facilitation and planning tips from both PREreview and your fellow Champions, as well as more resources to check out.

Live Reviews

Live Reviews are topic-centered, interactive preprint review calls via a video conference tool such as Zoom. Outputs from Live Reviews can be used to improve a manuscript or be integrated into journal review workflows.

Live Reviews allow structured and constructive discussions following [guided discussion questions](#) that encourage diverse methods of participation. Through these events, we strive to support and empower the voices of fellow researchers who have historically been underrepresented in scholarship and who are in the beginning stages of their research careers.

Who participates?

- Two facilitators with experience in hosting Live Reviews
- A topic expert (optional) to guide participants through a constructive discussion
- Preprint authors (optional) to gather live feedback on their preprint
- Researchers who join from all over the world to collaborate on improving a preprint, build their network, and meet globally renowned experts

What are the event outputs?

After the call, the organizing team works with the Live Review participants interested in authoring the review to summarize the discussion into a full PREREVIEW that is then published on [PREREVIEW.ORG](https://prereview.org). The reviewers will be listed as review authors using either their real name or their PREREVIEW pseudonym persona. In some cases, the review resulting from the call is integrated into the journal-organized peer review process—e.g., [a PREREVIEW included as reviewer #3 in the eLife peer review process on a bioRxiv preprint](#).

Resources for running a collaborative Live Review

If you are interested in running your own Live Review, you can do so online or in person (although please note that most of our materials are adapted to an online event). Below we list some templates that should help you get started. You can always reach out to us at community@prereview.org if you have any questions or require further support.

- [Live Review Timeline & Checklist](#)
- [Live Reviews Information Document](#)

- [Registration Form Text Template](#)
- [Email Templates for Live Review Authors](#)
- [Communication Plan Template](#)
- Event promotion templates ([LinkedIn post](#) & [Zoom banner](#))
- [Collaborative Writing Guide Template](#)
- [Review Composition Template](#)

PREreview Clubs

PREreview Clubs are collaborative preprint reviewing groups around a shared affiliation, affinity, interest, location, or any other common cause. Club members work together to give preprint authors timely, constructive peer feedback (sometimes via a format like our Live Reviews).

Anyone who wants to form a collaborative preprint reviewing group can ask to start a Club. While we plan to automate the process more, currently, PREreview Clubs are a concierge service. That means anyone looking to start a PREreview Club should [complete this form](#). We then get in touch via email to describe the next steps in the process and to make sure it's a good fit for what they want to achieve.

If everything seems right, we'll set up the Clubs page and go through the workflow with the Club Lead to ensure that the Club and all its participating authors are credited on the reviews they author together.

You can check out our [PREreview Clubs onboarding document](#) here to learn more.

You can also join an existing Club, take a look here for a [list of our current PREreview Clubs](#). Please note that some are open to others to join and will include a 'Join the club' button, whereas others may be closed.

Using the PREreview.org website

[PREreview.org](#) is the home of open, preprint reviews. At PREreview, we aim to establish a researcher-driven, participatory peer-review workflow, emphasizing the evaluation of expertise based on the quality of reviews rather than the identity of the reviewer or the prestige of their

affiliated research institution. We are creating a future in which every researcher is empowered with the skills to recognize and fight bias, and is welcomed into a peer review culture where constructive feedback is expected and rewarded.

Finding a preprint to review

Below, you can find a list of preprint servers that PREreview can easily pull public metadata information from for the purposes of review.

If you are searching for a preprint to review, please visit one of the servers listed below that's relevant to you! We can easily pull public metadata from all of these servers and frequently add more in response to user requests.

Alternatively, you can also check out our recent [Review Requests](#) on the PREreview website and also in our [#request-a-review channel](#) on the PREreview Community Slack to view author requests for feedback.

You can also visit [Society](#) to find curated lists of preprints you might like to review, especially through Society's [groups](#) and [lists](#).

Currently supported preprint servers:

- [Advance](#)
- [AfricArXiv](#)
- [Arcadia Science Pubs](#)
- [arXiv](#)
- [Authorea](#)
- [bioRxiv](#)
- [ChemRxiv](#)
- [Curvenote](#)
- [Dryad \(for dataset reviews\)](#)
- [EarthArXiv](#)
- [EcoEvoRxiv](#)
- [EdArXiv](#)
- [engrXiv](#)
- [Jxiv](#)
- [Lifecycle Journal](#)
- [medRxiv](#)
- [MetaArXiv](#)

- [NeuroLibre](#)
- [OSF](#)
- [PhilSci-Archive](#)
- [Preprints.org](#)
- [PsyArXiv](#)
- [PsychArchives](#)
- [Research Square](#)
- [SciELO](#)
- [ScienceOpen](#)
- [SocArXiv](#)
- [SSRN](#)
- [TechRxiv](#)
- [VeriXiv](#)
- [Zenodo](#)

If you or someone in your community uses a preprint server that is not listed and you would like PRereview.org to support this, please let us know at help@prereview.org.

Getting started with reviewing preprints

If you have a preprint in mind you would like to review, you can simply click '[Review a preprint](#)' and you will then be taken to a page asking you for the DOI of the preprint. Once you have entered that, it will ask you to log in or create an account if you have not already done so. Login is done via [ORCID](#). If you do not have a preprint in mind, but you wish to create a PRereview account in advance, you can click on the 'Log in' button on the top right to create your account.

Once you click the button, you'll be guided through a helpful workflow that will help you complete your review. You'll also have the option to start a Structured PRereview (with prompts from us), a Templated PRereview (with a basic, suggested framework from us), or a Freeform PRereview (with just a text box you can type in or copy/paste a PRereview you drafted elsewhere).

Once you have completed your review, you will be asked how you wish to author your review using either your public name associated with your ORCID iD or your PRereview pseudonym, which is a preassigned and uneditable combination of an animal and a color (e.g., Yellow Penguin). If you choose to publish a review with your pseudonym, your public name will remain hidden unless you disclose your pseudonym to others. You can visit the '[My details](#)' page to

edit your profile and decide which parts of your profile you'd like to share (or not). You can also preview your public and pseudonymous profiles so you know exactly how your profile displays for others and also [connect your profile to ORCID](#) to allow PREreview to update your ORCID profile with your public review activity automatically on your behalf.

You will also have the option to add any co-authors, declare any conflict of interests, and agree to our [Code of Conduct](#) before having a final chance to look over your review and click 'publish'. All reviews are assigned a DOI via [Zenodo](#), and you can find a list of [Recent PREreviews](#) on the website.

Our colleague Chad has recorded a [demo of the PREreview.org review workflow](#) if you wish to review or share this with others.

Read more about [how to use PREreview.org](#).

How PREreview works

Using Zoom (or other video conferencing software)

Zoom is a fairly intuitive and simple tool to use. That said, here are some tips based on what we have learned over the years:

- Ensure that all speakers join 10 minutes early to do a 'tech-check'. This means ensuring that everyone's audio and video settings are correct, and you may want to practice screen sharing to make sure that it is set up properly.
- Make sure when screen sharing your presentation that the audience can see the correct screen and that they see it full screen. Also, ensure you have it set up so that you are able to see any notes you need.
- In the Zoom meeting settings, you can choose to do things like allow Q&A as well as chat, and you may also wish to mute participants upon entry to cut down on background noise.
- Make sure recording is switched on (if you are recording) and that in the Zoom settings, recording notifications are turned on for all participants so that everyone is aware they are being recorded and can choose to leave the call if they do not give their consent.
- For events where the audience are not native English speakers, it can be useful to switch on the live captions during the meeting (please note this will only work in English and will not be perfect).
- Make sure you have someone to manage the Q&A and the chat so that the speakers can focus on presenting.
- When not speaking, it's good practice to mute your microphone to cut down on any background noise.
- A good tip is to make sure that you have the links to any resources you plan to share ready in advance, so you can simply copy/paste across to the chat.
- You can also set up polls in advance to engage your audience and get some quick feedback.
- If you are running a meeting with breakout rooms, you can let Zoom randomly allocate people during the meeting, or if you want people in set groups, then it's good to pre-assign participants to rooms in advance.

Zoom also has a lot of helpful online resources if you want to read more. They also run online training sessions fairly regularly and have several quick walkthrough videos. Here are some helpful guides:

- [Getting started guide for new users](#)

- [Managing breakout rooms](#)
- [Assigning polls and quizzes to specific meetings or webinars](#)
- [Change your language on Zoom](#)

Using Slack

At PREview, we regularly use [Slack](#) to communicate internally and also externally with our community members. In Slack, conversations are organized into channels depending on the topic or group of people involved. We have a private [#prereview-champions-2026](#) channel that you have been added to upon joining the Champions Program. We encourage you to use this channel to post questions to the team, get feedback on your plans, collaborate, problem-solve, or just chat about things that are going on in your life.

You can use Slack in a browser and download it to your desktop or phone. Here are some tips for using Slack:

- When setting up your profile, please choose a username that will be easy to identify you by (your email address will not be shared), an appropriate profile picture, and make sure that your account is set to the correct time zone so that Slack doesn't notify you at times when you are not available.
- To configure your notifications, simply click your name at the top left of the page and select 'Preferences' from the dropdown list. In the notifications section, you can then choose times when you don't want to be disturbed as well as set alerts for certain channels or keywords.
- You can also set a status to show when you're on holiday, sick, or otherwise busy so people know not to message you directly.
- Use threads to continue a conversation. You can reply directly to a message in the channel, which will create a thread, making it easier to follow the conversation.
- Don't feel you need to respond immediately to a message. Although Slack is a messaging application, interactions do not need to be synchronous, especially when we are working across a wide range of time zones.

- Please respect the shared space and the other members of the channel, including in any private communication. Please abide by our [Code of Conduct](#) at all times.

For more information, please refer to the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2020) Slack quick start guide. Woodley and Pratt doi:

[10.5281/zenodo.3763730](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3763730).

About PREreview

Our Mission

PREreview's mission is to bring more equity and transparency to scholarly peer review by supporting and empowering communities of researchers, particularly those at early stages of their career (ECRs) and historically excluded, to review preprints in a process that is rewarding to them. In 2017, we founded PREreview because we believe science and scholarship should be equitable, transparent, and collaborative.

Our Values

We believe in equal access

The fair distribution of advantages and relationships has the potential to change the face of scientific research. By providing pathways to mentorship, collaborative constructive feedback, and publishing of peer reviews, we are dedicated to expanding the reach of science from marginalized communities. We seek to level the playing field of the scientific community by offering resources that are often unavailable to marginalized scientists.

We believe in connecting people

Collaboration is a critical component of the research process. Scholarly conversation and feedback close unseen gaps and generate new ideas. As scientists, we know relationships cultivate dynamic and robust science. Toward that end, we are committed to building bridges between researchers and reviewers and mentors and mentees as a vital part of equity and scientific rigor.

We believe in self-reflection

Bias is a reality of our work and our world. We recognize this fact and work to alleviate its impact. Scientists who participate in our mentoring and training programs use action-oriented tools to mitigate the bias we all have when we mentor, peer review, and conduct ourselves on an everyday basis. We implement these steps in order to make our work and our field more equitable.

We believe in measurable success

Commitments to equity must be accompanied by data and action. We set our equity goals around key metrics that center on user inclusion and diverse demographics. At every level, our programming reflects an evidence-based approach and tangible benchmarks.

Our Team

Daniela Saderi
Executive Director,
Co-founder

Chad Sansing
Head of Product

Vanessa Fairhurst
Head of Community

Chris Wilkinson
Head of Technology

María Pía Tavella
Communications &
Engagement Officer

María Sol Ruiz
Champions Fellow
(Parental cover)

Samantha Hindle
Co-founder, AC
Secretary

Monica Granados
Co-founder, AC
Co-Chair

Kristen Ratan
AC member

Aurelia Munene
AC member

Christopher S. Marcum
AC Chair

Our core team is currently composed of five full-time employees: Daniela Saderi, Executive Director & Co-Founder, Chad Sansing, Head of Product, Vanessa Fairhurst, Head of Community, Chris Wilkinson, Head of Technology, and Pia Tavella, Communications and Engagement Officer.

While our Head of Community, Vanessa, is on parental leave, we also have María Sol Ruiz joining the PREreview Team in a part-time capacity to provide support, particularly with the Champions Program. Please contact Sol (champions@prereview.org) for any questions related to the program that you are unable to find the answer to here or with your mentor or Champions cohort.

We also rely on the wise advice and support of an Advisory Committee (AC), which currently includes Monica Granados (PREreview co-founder, AC Co-chair), Samantha Hindle (PREreview co-founder, AC Secretary), Christopher Steven Marcum, Aurelia Munene, and Kristen Ratan.

Full bios can be found on our [webpage](#).

How we are supported

PREreview operates as a non-profit as a fiscally sponsored project of [Code for Science & Society \(CS&S\)](#). CS&S is a 501(c)(3) nonprofit registered in the United States. CS&S provides administrative and strategic resources to project leads to support them in developing innovative technologies that benefit humanity. CS&S supports PREreview by assisting in building relationships with funding agencies, connecting us with the larger public interest tech community, as well as in hiring and management of staff.

Funders and sponsors

Gates Foundation

Other Useful Links

- Read our [2025 Annual report](#) for information on our achievements last year and our ongoing commitment to working in collaboration with our community to shape an equitable, open, and transparent scholarly evaluation landscape.
- The [PREreview Community Slack](#) is a great place for discussions about all things preprints and peer review, upcoming events, jobs, and opportunities, and to request feedback on your preprint or to share a review you have written.
- Our [Blog](#) is always a good place to go for news of new developments. If you have a good idea for a blog, you can always contact us and let us know!
- [Sign up for our bi-monthly newsletter](#) to be kept in the loop about our big developments and opportunities.

- You can also follow us on social media on [LinkedIn](#), [Mastodon](#), and [BlueSky](#), and subscribe to our [YouTube channel](#).

Shared Resources - More coming soon!

Please feel free to contribute to this list with links to other resources you think would be useful to your fellow Champions.

Peer Review:

- [PLOS Peer Review Center](#)
- [COPE Ethical guidelines for peer reviewers](#)
- [‘Editorial Peer Reviewers as Shepherds, Rather Than Gatekeepers’](#)
- [Okune, Angela. \(2019\). Self-Review of Citational Practice. Zenodo](#)

Facilitation & Events:

- [Open Peer Reviewers in Africa Workshop Trainer Guide](#)
- [Sansing, Chad. \(2020\). 5 Tips For Designing Engaging, Inclusive Sessions](#)
- [Aurora, Valerie, and Gardiner, Mary. How to Respond to Code of Conduct Reports](#)
- [Ahenkorah, Elise \(2020\). “Safe and Brave Spaces Don’t Work \(and What You Can Do Instead\)”](#)
- [Harvard. Calling In and Calling Out Guide](#)
- [Makled, Laila R. \(2023\). Impactful Gathering and Facilitation Resource Guide](#)
- [Makled, Laila R. \(2023\). The basics of an impactful agenda: structure & timing](#)
- [The Open Organization Leaders Manual](#)
- [CSCCE. Organizing Community Events](#)
- [The Carpentries. Recommendations for Teaching Carpentries Workshops Online](#)
- [Delipalta, A., & Herterich, P. \(2021\). Planning hybrid events](#)

DEIA:

- [DEIA and Doing the Right Thing](#)
- [Open Science and Open Source only with Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Accessibility](#)
- [C4 DISC Toolkits for Equity](#)

Mentoring:

